
INNOVATIVE HUMAN RESOURCE MANAGEMENT AND EMPLOYEE PRODUCTIVITY OF FOOD AND BEVERAGE SECTOR IN RIVERS STATE.

By

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Abstract

The study investigates the relationship between innovative human resource management and employee productivity in the food and beverage sector in Rivers State. Process and technological innovation were used as the dimensions of IHRM, while employee commitment and competency were used as the measures of productivity. The survey study accessible populations comprise 540 employees of a food and beverage firm in Rivers State. A sample of 226 was derived using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. The primary data was obtained using a well-structured questionnaire. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability level of 0.7 was used, and Spearman's rank correlation analyses were used for the analyses. The findings revealed that both processes and technological innovation have a strong, significant relationship with employee productivity. The study concludes that innovative human resource management and employee productivity in the food and beverage sector in Rivers State. The study recommends enhancing both process and technological innovation for employee productivity.

Keywords: Innovative Human Resource Management, Process Innovation, Technological Innovation, Employee Productivity, Employee Commitment, Employee, Competency.

1.0 Introduction

The food and beverage (F&B) industry is a major driver of economic growth, industrial output, and consumer goods. It is also one of the biggest labour employers globally. The productivity of this sector determined the firm's success. Productivity determines efficiency by maintaining competitiveness, meeting consumer demand, and adapting to economic pressures. A labour-intensive and fast-paced sector requires productivity effectiveness, as marginal gains in employee productivity enhance increased output, customer satisfaction and profitability (Ogunbiyi-Davies et al., 2023). Employee productivity is needed in an industry characterised by high customer expectations, rapid and flexible production cycles, and strict compliance with food safety standards. Effective workforce performance guarantees consistency in the production of high-quality goods while reducing wastage and operational errors. Employee productivity in F&B firms directly affects not only output levels but also organisational sustainability, as the efficiency of workers determines the firm's competitiveness in an environment with high labour costs and constant market pressures.

The F&B sector, which accounts for a large proportion of manufacturing activity, requires the productivity of their employees, as their productivity has wider economic implications. Higher workforce efficiency promotes better job stability, industrial growth, and poverty reduction through the multiplier effects of improved firm performance (Dike-Worlu, 2024). A motivated, skilled, and engaged employee puts in their best to ensure the firm's innovativeness, higher market share, and ability to be competitive with international brands. When productivity is low, it often results in lower profitability, weakened capacity to respond to the dynamic business environment, and high staff turnover; this threatens the long-term sustainability of the firms. Enhancing employee productivity should be viewed not just as a managerial concern, but as a strategic imperative for the entire sector.

Globalisation and digital transformation are now reshaping the food and beverage sector, making it a necessity to recognise that their competitive advantages lie not only in technology and infrastructure but also in the human capital that drives operations. Investing in training, reward systems, and collaborative workplace practices is an enabler of productivity, financial performance, and organisational resilience (Mehari et al., 2024; Oloidi et al., 2025). Hence, prioritising employee productivity is essential for sustainability and competitiveness. However, despite this fact, many faces hurdles and constant struggles are experienced by the F&B, as they experience inadequate skilled workers, high wage expenses and high staff turnover. The problem is worsened by the COVID-19 pandemic as it changes employees' expectations and reveals the inadequacies of the traditional workforce models (Society for Human Resource Management [SHRM], 2021). The unstable labour market and operational pressures require the F&B to be innovative, proactive, and effective in their human resource management (HRM). This made it a strategic necessity in enhancing a high firm's productivity and competitiveness (Dike-Worlu, 2024).

The Yona et al. (2024) study emphasises that the human resource information system (HRIS) enhances employees' creativity, job satisfaction, and productivity. Likewise, Huynh et al. (2025) suggest that the use of digital HRM methods in an organisation can promote enhanced decision-making and productivity results within the firm. Inculcating strategic HRM procedures and approaches in training, development, and welfare investments yields an impact on the financial performance and employee productivity of many firms (Ogunbiyi-Davies, Alao, Aremu, & Olalere, 2023). The F&B requires usage of rapid production cycles, adherence to stringent food safety requirements, and timely work efficiency (Yona et al.,

2024). Having customised HR interventions, such as team coordination mechanisms, safety and health programs, and competency-based training, promotes reduced factory errors, decreases poor product quality, and bolsters staff productivity (Huynh et al., 2025). According to Oyedokun et al. (2025), innovative reward systems have improved productivity relative to conventional financial incentives, highlighting the importance of having HRM frameworks.

HR innovations in every organisation must align with local socioeconomic circumstances. Team collaboration and training must be adapted to local needs for effectiveness and staff productivity (Dike-Worlu, 2024). This topic highlights how cultural and contextual elements significantly impact HR outcomes. Oloidi et al. (2025) posit that employee engagement facilitates productivity, and the result is influenced by work flexibility and the worker's experience. The study showed that workplace ethics, when supported by workforce diversity, enhance organisational performance in Ethiopian food and beverage companies. This To enhance efficiency, HRM innovations should integrate inclusivity and ethical standards to achieve sustainable results (Mehari et al., 2024). Although several studies (Yona et al., 2024; Oyedokun et al., 2025; Oloidi et al., 2025) have examined the influence of HRIS, there remains a lack of research directly linking these practices to productivity outcomes in food and beverage operations in Rivers State. Therefore, this study aims to fill the identified knowledge gap and offer management in those institutions practical insights into cost-effective HR methods that enhance productivity while also aiding policymakers in strengthening workforce development initiatives.

1.1 Statement of the Problem

The food and beverage (F&B) sector often face low staff productivity problems. Studies have shown that many F&B frequently exhibit low performance because of unfavourable working conditions, diminished poor motivation and inadequate operational and administrative knowledge and skills. Uzochukwu et al.'s (2023) study observed that in the Nigerian hospitality sector, reward systems influence the quality of provided service and the dedication of employees at the workplace. When organisations are not productive, it becomes difficult to meet the expected quality, operational and consumer needs.

Low staff productivity results in operational inefficiencies, poor services, higher cost of production, inability to meet the client satisfaction and diminished profitability. When services are poor, it harms the customer loyalty and reduces the firm's competitive advantage.

Adebayo and Waheed (2023) suggested that flexible working options influenced job satisfaction and productivity. When there is low productivity, production declines, absenteeism increases, and staff turnover is high. However, not addressing low productivity in time could result in higher waste, lower service and production quality and low profitability. Moreover, staff productivity also affects the economy and job growth. Unproductivity could result in staff layoffs, diminished operations or investments in growth, low employment, lesser availability of quality foods, higher prices of food, and lower earnings. Poor productivity discourages investment, hence leading to shortages of funds, and when there are low funds to run the firm, it has adverse effects and results in not being productive. Akintoye (2024), in his study, observed the need for work specialisation, favourable work circumstances, and skills correlated with employee productivity.

Despite productivity problem awareness, the solutions offered have failed to resolve the problems in the F & B firms, as many firms are still using traditional HR techniques, poor training and development, low incentive systems, poor performance evaluations, and poor motivational programmes. Enhanced higher pay, job satisfaction, and improved career advancement will enable the workers to be more productive. Uzochukwu et al. (2023) suggest that higher pay raises and promotions can improve service delivery and dedication. Furthermore, Adebayo and Waheed (2023) assert that providing flexible work schedules can enhance employee happiness and productivity. But often, several initiatives used in the F&B are insufficient to make the workers effective; hence, the study aims to tackle the issue by identifying and assessing new human resource management techniques and finding out creative new ideas that will work best to boost staff productivity in food and beverage firms in Rivers State. This will assist managers in choosing HRM methods that are both suited for the situation and long-lasting.

1.2 Aim and Objectives of the Study.

The aim of the study is to examine the relationship between innovative human resources management and employee productivity in the food and beverage sector in Rivers State. The specific objectives of the study are to:

- i. Examine the relationship between process innovation and employee commitment of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.
- ii. Determine the relationship between process innovation and employee competency of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.
- iii. Examine the relationship between technological innovation and employee commitment of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.
- iv. Determine the relationship between technological innovation and employee competency at the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.

1.3 Research Questions

The study posed the following research questions.

- i. What is the relationship between process innovation and employee commitment at the food and beverage firm in Rivers State?
- ii. How does process innovation relate to the employee competency of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State?
- iii. How does technological innovation relate to the employee commitment of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State?
- iv. What is the relationship between technological innovation and employee competency of the food and beverage firms in Rivers State?

1.4 Research Hypotheses

This study asserted and tested the following research hypotheses:

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between process innovation and employee commitment of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.

H₀₂: There is no significant relationship between process innovation and employee competency of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.

H₀₃: There is no significant relationship between technological innovation and employee commitment of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.

H₀₄: There is no significant relationship between technological innovation and employee competency of the food and beverage firm in Rivers State.

Conceptual Framework

Figure 1.1: Conceptual framework for innovative human resources management and employee productivity

Source: Researchers (2025)

2.0 Review of Related Literature

2.1 Conceptual Review

Innovative Human Resource Management

Innovative Human Resource Management refers to HR practices that extend beyond the usual tasks to include new ideas like employee-driven innovation and commitment, flexible work arrangements, use of digital HR tools, learning culture, and adaptable HR policies. Koster and Innovative HRM are a collection of HR practices distinguished by their metrics, determinants, and results. Organisations experiencing increased size, high external pressure, and enhanced organisational stability are more inclined to implement innovative HRM practices (Benda, 2020) through collaboration, organisational learning, and the integration of HR technology.

Innovative HRM enhances creativity, proactiveness, organisational adaptability, and high productivity. Organisations can create a culture of continuous improvement and high employee engagement by using HRM practices that are responsive, forward-looking, and focused on their employees. Innovative HRM serves as a positive predictor of organisational innovation. When an organisation practises continual renewal of HR services, there is a tendency to introduce new products, processes, or business models (Koster and Benda, 2020). Hence, innovative HRM functions as a strategic lever in dynamic sectors or environments to

enhance competitive advantage, boost employee morale, decrease attrition, and elevate productivity.

Process innovation

Process innovations are new or greatly improved ways to make and deliver products and services. This involves making modifications in production, changing to digital tools and software, and enhancing new efficient processes that reduce costs, waste, or lead time, or make things better and more flexible. The OECD/Eurostat says innovations in human resource practices are a category of innovation, along with product, marketing, and organisational innovation. Process innovation efficiency reduces costs, makes operations more efficient, improves quality, and makes a company more competitive. For example, the study by Iherobiem and Sanusi (2023) demonstrated that firms implementing improved process flows, upgrading equipment, or adopting leaner production workflows achieved statistically higher performance outcomes. Process innovation could mean better layouts for manufacturing lines, better scheduling of food processing steps, better supply chain workflows, automation of some operations, or better cleanliness and safety practices that cut down on spoilage. These modifications not only cut down on waste (of materials and time), but they also increase throughput, uniformity, and, in the end, profits.

Technological Innovation

Technological innovation refers to the use and creation of new technologies and enhancements to existing technology. This involves the use of information systems, novel machinery equipment, automation, digital tools (software, data analytics), and various technology-driven methodologies to transform work processes. When new technologies are used, workers' skills improve rapidly, but it could be less effective innovation without the right training (Onaolapo and Adeyinka, 2020). Technological innovation enhances efficiency, product quality, consistency, speed of service and capacity, and lesser mistakes and waste; it also makes it easier to follow rules and increases production per unit of time. However, efficiency in new technology usage requires other investments, such as educating staff, keeping things running, and managing change, as gaps in staff skills or aversion to new technology can slow progress (Onaolapo and Adeyinka, 2020).

Employee productivity

Employee productivity refers to how well and quickly employees turn inputs (time, effort, and materials) into outputs (goods, services, and customer satisfaction). Productivity is often measured by each worker's productivity, work efficiency and effectiveness, speed, number of wastes and mistakes made, and the costs per unit of output. Productivity affects an organisation's profitability, competitiveness, and ability to grow. Sime and Tadesse (2025) examine the influence of firm-level innovation on labour productivity and employment, revealing that process innovation has a positive impact on the workers' productivity. Enhancing the use of new production technology often increases productivity growth (van Zyl, 2023). Employee productivity is vital in the F&B sector, as profit margins are often small, preferences and demand can be small or seasonal, food safety is critical, and consumers are sensitive to quality and punctuality.

Employee Commitment

Employee commitment refers to the psychological attachment, loyalty, or binding relationship between employees and their organisation. This includes their intention to exert extra effort, stay, identify and uphold organisational goals and values. Meyer and Allen's three-component model, which encompasses affective, continuance, and normative

commitment, are important measures of employee commitment. Employee commitment is also influenced by organisational climate, mobility opportunities, and intrinsic and extrinsic motivators (Inegbedion, 2022). Employee commitment is vital for productivity, as committed employees tend to be more persistent, more productive, less likely to leave, adaptable to change, and more likely to engage in discretionary behaviours. Service, hygiene, speed, reliability and commitment in the F&B can mean fewer absences, more attentiveness, more consistency in performance, and better-quality control. Commitment moderates how innovative practices are adopted (Oyuru & Ambali, 2021).

Employee Competency

Employee competency refers to the combination of knowledge, abilities, skills, and behaviours required to perform roles effectively by the employees. Competency includes technical skills, soft skills, teamwork, problem-solving abilities, knowledge of safety and quality standards, adaptability, leadership, and initiative. It is the core driver of performance because competent employees are more efficient, make fewer errors, adapt better to change, and readily take advantage of innovation. Putra et al.'s (2025) study revealed that employee competence had a positive significant effect on work productivity and performance in hotels. Similarly, in the Nigerian F&B context and adjacent sectors, HR practice studies often indicate that training and skill development (which build competency) are among key HRM levers in improving productivity and commitment.

2.2 Resource-Based View (RBV) theory

Resource-Based View (RBV) theory, developed by Barney in 1991, states that competitive advantage does not merely come from external market positioning but from how well an organisation harnesses its unique internal resources. Innovative HRM practices view employees' commitment, competencies, and congruence as critical outcomes, positioning them as key productivity drivers. Firms that develop HR systems that are not imitated by competitors, such as unique engagement models or advanced technology platforms, can sustain superior performance over time (Wright, et al., 2001). In relation to the present study, the RBV is useful in explaining why process innovation and technological innovation are critical predictors of employee productivity. These practices represent valuable and rare organisational resources that enhance employee outcomes such as commitment, competency, and congruence. By adopting innovative HRM strategies, organisations in today's competitive environment can maximise productivity while creating systems that are not easily replicated by competitors (Jiang & Messersmith, 2018).

2.3 Empirical Review

Mohammed & Tahir (2024) investigated "human resource practices and employee productivity: A case of SMEs". A quantitative, cross-sectional survey design was used. The study focused on small and medium-sized enterprises (SMEs) located in various governorates of Oman, with the population consisting of employees and proprietors of these SMEs. Using cluster random sampling (clusters chosen from all governorates with random draws inside clusters), the authors obtained 383 completed questionnaires. Data were collected via a structured questionnaire that was administered. Data analysis was carried out using SPSS (frequency, descriptive, correlation, and regression analyses). The study found that innovative HR practices have a positive and statistically significant effect on employee outcomes. The study concludes that adopting selected innovative HR practices can materially improve SME employee outcomes and productivity. The study recommends that SME managers should

invest in targeted innovative HR tactics and design culturally appropriate training and rewards, and that policymakers should support HR capability building in SMEs.

Mahvish et al. (2023) studied the impact of innovation-orientated human resources on small and medium enterprises' performance. (The research used a quantitative survey design applied to SMEs in the twin cities (Islamabad and Rawalpindi), Pakistan. The population comprises 348 SMEs. Analyses used OLS regression and logistic regression (different models for continuous productivity and binary innovation outcomes), plus robustness checks and model specifications. Findings showed that innovative HR practices are generally associated with better firm performance. The study concludes that not all "innovative" HR practices automatically boost every type of firm performance; context and practice design matter. The study recommends prioritising innovative recruitment and carefully designing redeployment, retraining, and reward systems to avoid unintended negative effects, and SMEs should focus HR innovation where it most aligns with desired performance outcomes.

Rogozińska-Pawelczyk (2024) examines innovative human resource management practices, organisational support, and knowledge worker efforts to counteract job burnout in the Polish business services sector. The target population was 1000 knowledge workers employed by BSS organisations in Poland. Data were gathered via CAWI using validated scales; the analyses employed confirmatory factor analysis and structural equation modelling (SEM) in AMOS (CFA, fit indices, bootstrapping for indirect effects). Results showed robust negative direct effects of IHRMP on burnout and significant full mediation through organisational support and employee effort. The study recommends implementing IHRMP along with policies that enhance perceived organisational support.

Vadithe & Kesari (2025) investigate the impact of HR analytics on organisational performance in the IT sector: The study was a cross-sectional survey design focused on IT sector employees in India. The population comprises IT sector employees; the study reports data collected from 355 respondents. The methods of analysis were variance-based/PLS-SEM (SmartPLS) and hierarchical/statistical modelling to test direct and mediating effects. Findings indicate significant positive relationships. It revealed that HR analytics usage predicts higher employee engagement and motivation, which in turn predict better organisational performance. The study concludes that HR analytics is a strategic capability that improves employee outcomes and organisational results when channelled through engagement and motivation. The study recommended building HR analytics capability, training HR professionals in analytics, aligning analytics outputs to interventions that boost engagement/motivation, and pursuing longitudinal studies to establish causality more firmly.

3.0 Methodology

This study employed a cross-sectional survey. The accessible populations comprise 540 employees of a food and beverage firm in Rivers State. A sample of 226 was derived using the Krejcie and Morgan (1970) table. The primary data was obtained using a well-structured questionnaire. The independent variable, innovative human resource management, was operationalised using two dimensions: process innovation and technological innovation. Each construct was measured with a set of five items. Process innovation was assessed with items such as, "Our organisation regularly introduces new methods to improve workflow efficiency." Similarly, technological innovation was measured with items such as "Our organisation invests in modern digital tools to improve performance." The criterion variable, employee productivity, was measured using two dimensions: employee commitment and employee competency. Employee commitment was assessed with items such as "I am willing

to put in extra effort to help the organisation succeed.” Employee competency was also measured with items such as “I have the necessary skills to perform my job effectively.” Face and content validity were used to determine the validity of the instrument used in this investigation. The reliability was determined using Cronbach's alpha. The Cronbach's Alpha reliability level of 0.7 was used in the investigation. Values above 7.0 are considered composite reliability. Spearman’s rank correlation analyses were used for the analysis.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1 Result

226 questionnaires were distributed, but only 221 (97.8%) copies were returned, and this constitutes the valid questionnaire. The hypotheses test is undertaken at a 95.5% confidence interval, and the decision rule is stated below.

Where $P < 0.05$ = Reject the null hypotheses.

Where $P > 0.05$ = Accept the null hypotheses.

Table 1: Correlations Between Process innovation and Dimensions Of Employee productivity

		Process Innovation	Employee Commitment	Employee Competency
Spearman's Rho	Process Innovation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.865**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000
		N	221	221
	Employee Commitment	Correlation Coefficient	.865**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.
		N	221	221
	Employee Competency	Correlation Coefficient	.855**	.835**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000
		N	221	221

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

Process innovation and Employee commitment: As shown in table 1, the Spearman’s rho value is 0.865 ($p = 0.000$), which is less than the significance threshold of 0.05. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.748, indicating that approximately 74.8% of the variation in employee commitment can be explained by process innovation. Based on these results, the null hypothesis (H_{01}) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_{a1}) is accepted. This indicates a significant and positive relationship between process innovation and employee commitment.

Process innovation and Employee competency: Table 1 reveals a Spearman’s rho value of **0.855** ($p = 0.000$), which is also below the alpha level of 0.05. The r^2 value of 0.731 suggests that 73.1% of the variance in employee competency is attributable to process innovation. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_{02}) is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis.

This confirms a strong and positive relationship between process innovation and employee competency.

Table 2: Correlations between Technological innovation and the Dimension of Employee productivity

		technological innovation	employee commitment	employee competency	
Spearman's rho	Technological Innovation	Correlation Coefficient	1.000	.895**	.875**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.	.000	.000
		N	221	221	221
	Employee Commitment	Correlation Coefficient	.895**	1.000	.840**
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.	.000
		N	221	221	221
	Employee Competency	Correlation Coefficient	.875**	.840**	1.000
		Sig. (2-tailed)	.000	.000	.
		N	221	221	221

** . Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

Source: SPSS Output, 2025.

Technological innovation and Employee commitment: According to table 2, the Spearman's rho value is 0.895 ($p = 0.000$), which is below the significance level of 0.05. The coefficient of determination (r^2) is 0.801, indicating that 80.1% of the variation in employee commitment is explained by technological innovation. Given this result, the null hypothesis (H_{03}) is rejected, and the alternative hypothesis (H_{a3}) is accepted. This observation demonstrates a strong and significant positive relationship between technological innovation and employee commitment.

Technological innovation and Employee competency: As shown in table 2, the Spearman's rho value is 0.875 ($p = 0.000$), which is less than the 0.05 significance level. The r^2 value is 0.765, indicating that technological innovation accounts for 76.5% of the variation in employee competency. Based on this evidence, the null hypothesis (H_{04}) is rejected in favour of the alternative hypothesis. This suggests that there is a strong, significant and positive relationship between technological innovation and employee competency.

4.2 Discussion of Finding

The findings indicate that process innovation has a significant and positive impact on process innovation and Employee commitment in the food and beverage firms in Rivers State. With Spearman's rho values of 0.865 and 0.855, respectively. The findings revealed that both process innovation and technological innovation correlate with staff productivity (commitment and competency). The correlation coefficients for all the associations that were investigated are positive, strong, and statistically significant at the 0.01 level, showing the importance of innovation-driven HRM strategies on the improvement of workforce productivity. The strong coefficients of determination (74.8% for commitment and 73.1% for competency) show that enhancements of process innovation correlate with productivity, increased motivation, loyalty, and skill development. This aligns with Iherobiem and Sanusi

(2023), whose work shows that work processes enhance productivity and cultivate employee commitment to organisational objectives. Furthermore, Santos-Vijande and Álvarez-González (2021) revealed that constant use of improved work process innovations makes employees be in line with the company's goals, thus increasing production levels.

The findings also revealed that technological innovation has a positive significant influence on workers' commitment and competency, with correlation values of 0.895 and 0.875, respectively. This implies that the adoption and integration of technology enhance employee engagement and skill development. With determination values of 80.1% for commitment and 76.5% for competency, the result revealed that the implementation of digital tools, automation, and training programmes significantly enhances employee commitment and competency. These results conform with the findings of Onaolapo and Adeyinka (2020) that technology innovation improves staff flexibility and efficiency. It also aligns with Putra et al. (2025), who say that employees who use modern digital tools in their jobs help the organisation do even better. The results also fit with global trends that tend to be more productive (Zhang et al., 2022).

Collectively, these findings highlight the significance of creative HRM practices (process innovation and technological innovations) as facilitators of employee productivity. The findings substantiate the resource-based view (RBV), which posits that organisations get a competitive advantage by developing distinctive and valuable internal skills (Barney, 1991).

5.0 Conclusion

This study examined the impact of innovative human resource management on employee productivity in the food and beverage sectors in Rivers State. The dimensions of IHRM in the study are process innovation and technological innovation, while the measures are productivity. The findings revealed that both process and technological innovation correlate with employee productivity. Process innovation led to big changes in employee commitment (74.8%) and competency (73.1%), whereas technical innovation led to even bigger changes in employee commitment (80.1%) and competency (76.5%). These results show how important it is for HRM practices to include innovation to improve workforce outcomes. The findings revealed that the food and beverage companies that use innovative HRM methods improve employee productivity. Process innovation keeps people interested by constantly improving workflows, while technological innovation gives them tools and skills that help them be more flexible and do better work. Both process and technological innovation make HRM more dynamic and competitive. Hence, the food and beverage firms should use innovative HRM to keep their employees productive and their businesses successful in a world that is becoming more competitive and technology-driven.

6.0 Recommendations

1. The food and beverage firms should institutionalise continuous process improvement programmes that actively involve employees in workflow redesign. This could be achieved through engagement of staff in problem-solving and idea generation to build stronger emotional attachment and loyalty to the firm, thereby enhancing employee commitment.
2. Managers should integrate mentoring and structured training programmes for new processes that are introduced to ensure employees develop the necessary skills to adapt to changing workflows, thereby increasing their competency and job effectiveness.

3. Organisations should invest not only in acquiring new technologies but also in change management strategies that emphasise employee involvement and support, as providing incentives for technology adoption and recognising early adopters can strengthen employees' willingness to stay committed to the organisation.
4. Firms should prioritise regular digital upskilling programmes to ensure that employees can effectively utilise new technologies, as this will not only enhance their technical competency but also improve adaptability, productivity, and long-term competitiveness in the sector.

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